

IGSN–DataCite Archaeology CoP Crosswalk Recommendation

22 September 2025 – Version 1.0

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	2
1.1 Scope of the Crosswalk	3
2. DataCite Mandatory Properties	4
2.1 DataCite:Identifier	4
2.2 DataCite:Creator	4
2.3 DataCite:Title	4
2.4 DataCite:Publisher	4
2.5 DataCite:PublicationYear	5
2.6 DataCite:resourceType and DataCite:resourceTypeGeneral	5
3. DataCite Recommended Properties	5
3.1 DataCite:Subject	5
3.2 DataCite:Contributor	6
3.3 DataCite:Date	7
3.4 DataCite:relatedIdentifier	7
3.5 DataCite:Description	8
3.6 DataCite:geoLocation	8
4. ArchProfile Mandatory Properties	8
4.1 ArchProfile:Project	8
4.2 ArchProfile:investigationDates	9
4.3 ArchProfile:collectorExcavator	10
4.4 ArchProfile:Publisher	10
4.5 ArchProfile:sampleTitle	10
4.6 ArchProfile:otherIdentifier	10
4.7 ArchProfile:collectionDate	10
4.8 ArchProfile:sampleMaterialType	10
5. ArchProfile Recommended Properties	10
5.1 ArchProfile:investigationType	10
5.2 ArchProfile:Contributor	11

5.3 ArchProfile:Description	11
5.4 ArchProfile:Subject	11
5.5 ArchProfile:collectionMethod	11
5.6 ArchProfile:stratigraphicContext	11
5.7 ArchProfile:sampleDepth	12
5.8 ArchProfile:sampleWeight	12
5.9 ArchProfile:Colour	12
5.10 ArchProfile:absoluteDating	13
5.11 ArchProfile:relativeDating	13
5.12 ArchProfile:currentStatus	13
5.13 ArchProfile:Relations	13
Annex A – CoP Members	13

1. Introduction

The [IGSN–DataCite Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Community of Practice](#) (hereinafter ‘Archaeology CoP’) has been meeting monthly since March 2022. It is composed of a small group of archaeologists and cultural heritage researchers with backgrounds in areas such as archaeometry, landscape archaeology, and data management from prehistoric to modern eras, and with an interest in material sample management, data collection, and publication.

Among the primary aims of the Archaeology CoP has been to develop a description for archaeological and cultural heritage samples in terms of a standardized metadata profile, taking in account disciplinary-specific use cases and workflows. The CoP has published [Version 1.0 of the Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile](#) alongside this Recommendation.

This current Recommendation builds on the Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile, with the goal for the Archaeology CoP to reach consensus on a crosswalk to support the translation of the Metadata Profile into the DataCite Schema V4.6 for the purposes of registering IGSN IDs for archaeological samples. Mirroring the work of the IGSN–DataCite Partnership Working Group in producing its [Recommendation](#), the Archaeology CoP firstly populated the six mandatory DataCite elements (Identifier, Creator, Title, Publisher, publicationYear, and resourceType), before then populating the six recommended DataCite elements

(`Subject`, `Contributor`, `Date`, `relatedIdentifier`, `Description`, and `geoLocation`). All members of the Archaeology CoP agreed on the Recommendation described in this document.

1.1 Scope of the Crosswalk

Following the IGSN–DataCite Crosswalk Recommendation, for ease of reference, the Archaeology CoP has assigned the ‘namespaces’ `DataCite` for properties originating from the DataCite Metadata Schema and `ArchProfile` for properties from the Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile.

Mappings for the mandatory and recommended properties in `DataCite` are given in Sections 2 and 3, respectively. Sections 4 and 5 then give (respective) mappings back to the mandatory and recommended properties of `ArchProfile` for consistency and completeness.

It should be noted that `ArchProfile` was developed by the Archaeology CoP with a focus purely on what one needs to fully and accurately describe archaeological and cultural heritage samples; specifically, without the restrictions of adhering to any existing metadata schemata. Nevertheless, the CoP was also cognizant of not ignoring the work of others and ‘reinventing the wheel’ when a perfectly good solution or method exists, while the notion of ultimately registering IGSN IDs for samples was also in the background of the CoP’s thinking when designing `ArchProfile`.

As a result of the above, there are several cases where `ArchProfile` has been heavily influenced or taken wholly from `DataCite`. Furthermore, the Archaeology CoP felt strongly about the need to promote uniformity in the metadata descriptions for archaeological samples, and leverage the immense work by various communities to generate controlled vocabularies and ontologies. The CoP therefore took the decision that, where possible, `ArchProfile` properties should follow existing vocabularies and map to the `DataCite:Subject` property.

Finally, although `ArchProfile` contains a number of properties referring to the collection site, the profile has been designed for a material sample only. This is mainly due to the obligations of the properties—as well as the limited descriptive elements—which would be different if describing an archaeological collection site. The Archaeology CoP will create a separate profile for collection sites, with properties and obligations revised to reflect the information that should (and can) be

captured. In reality, it would be expected that both a collection site and material sample are registered with persistent identifiers and linked within their metadata, such that certain properties are inherited by the sample from the site.

2 DataCite Mandatory Properties

2.1 DataCite: Identifier

The Archaeology CoP did not include an equivalent of this property in `ArchProfile`, rather it is expected that `DataCite:Identifier` is automatically populated with a DOI upon the creation of an IGSN ID metadata record within DataCite services.

2.2 DataCite: Creator

The `ArchProfile:collectorExcavator` property is defined as ‘Details of the creator(s), compiler(s), funding agencies, or other bodies or people intellectually responsible for the sample collection. Used to properly credit individuals and institutions for their contribution to the resource’. Although the Archaeology CoP proposes that the subproperties of `DataCite:Creator` be expanded (see below), it made the decision to directly align the content of `ArchProfile:collectorExcavator` and `DataCite:Creator`.

To better capture the types of people and organizations that are considered to be an archaeological sample’s ‘creators’, the Archaeology CoP suggests to add a ‘Role’ or ‘Type’ subproperty to `DataCite:Creator` (similar to `DataCite:Contributor`) in future versions of the DataCite Metadata Schema. It would also be helpful to the archaeology and cultural heritage communities if the following subproperties were considered: ‘Address’, ‘Phone’, ‘Fax’, ‘Email’, ‘URL’ (authoritative website of the person or organization named). Such properties are expected to capture institutional rather than personal information.

2.3 DataCite: Title

`DataCite:Title` = `ArchProfile:sampleTitle` for an archaeological sample.

2.4 DataCite: Publisher

The `ArchProfile:Publisher` property contains ‘The organization that is registering the metadata record for the sample’ and maps directly to `DataCite:Publisher`.

2.5 DataCite: PublicationYear

The Archaeology CoP did not include an equivalent of the `DataCite:PublicationYear` property in `ArchProfile`. However, it follows the IGSN–DataCite Crosswalk Recommendation, whereby `DataCite:PublicationYear` is the year that the archaeological sample was registered with a persistent identifier; unless, it was otherwise made available to the community prior to this.

2.6 DataCite: resourceType and DataCite: resourceTypeGeneral

Following the standard convention agreed by the IGSN–DataCite partnership, `DataCite:resourceTypeGeneral` = ‘PhysicalObject’ for all archaeological samples registered with IGSN IDs. For the `DataCite:resourceType` property, an IGSN ID registrant is strongly recommended to minimally use either ‘Archaeological Object’ or ‘Archaeological Site’ to differentiate between these sampling concepts and facilitate searches across all archaeological samples. To supplement basic classification, a registrant may also add terms from the standard ontology or vocabulary that is most common within their discipline or community to typify material samples.

It should be noted here that while archaeological sites do not fall under the purview of the current Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile, the concept will be required for a site-specific profile.

3. DataCite Recommended Properties

When performing the crosswalk to the recommended properties of the DataCite Metadata Schema, it was immediately apparent that often several Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile properties may be captured. This section therefore focuses on the primary `ArchProfile` property in each case. The crosswalk to the `ArchProfile` recommended properties in Section 5 elaborates on all of the mappings.

3.1 DataCite: Subject

Similar to the IGSN–DataCite Crosswalk Recommendation, `DataCite:Subject` is primarily equivalent to the mandatory `ArchProfile:sampleMaterialType` property, which contains the materials that compose the sample. According to what

information is included in

`ArchProfile:sampleMaterialType.materialClassification`, the subproperties `DataCite:Subject.subjectScheme`, `schemeURI`, `valueURI`, and `classificationCode` should, as appropriate, capture the schema and value used to categorize the materials.

Other `ArchProfile` properties that may be included in `DataCite:Subject` are:

- [ArchProfile:investigationType](#)
- [ArchProfile:Subject](#)
- [ArchProfile:collectionMethod](#)
- [ArchProfile:Colour](#)
- [ArchProfile:relativeDating](#)

This list is not exhaustive and focuses only on top-level recommended properties. It is also the case for similar lists within the document.

3.2 DataCite:Contributor

As for `DataCite:Creator`, the Archaeology CoP ultimately took the decision to align `ArchProfile:Contributor` with `DataCite:Contributor`. In particular, the mandatory subproperties `ArchProfile:Contributor.Role` and `ArchProfile:Contributor.Name` are, respectively, equivalent to `DataCite:Contributor.contributorType` and `DataCite:Contributor.contributorName`. In addition to encouraging the use of identifiers such as ORCID IDs and ROR IDs, it would again be helpful to the archaeology and cultural heritage communities if the following subproperties were considered within `DataCite` to capture institutional information: 'Address', 'Phone', 'Fax', 'Email', 'URL'.

The Archaeology CoP would also like some additions to the `contributorType` controlled vocabulary to better match the roles seen within the archaeological and cultural heritage (sub)disciplines:

- Excavator: There should be separation between who excavated an object and `DataCollector`, which in the Archaeology and Cultural Heritage field, refers more to the person who is conducting analyses on the object.
- Heritage Authority: The legal body who is managing the object and is in charge of (for example) issuing the license to take the object from an excavation or subsample an object for analysis. The existing role of 'RightsHolder' might be updated to better cover the handling of objects in such ways.

3.3 DataCite:Date

At a minimum, the mandatory `ArchProfile:investigationDates` and `ArchProfile:collectionDate` properties will be contained within `DataCite:Date`, each with an appropriate `dateType` ([see Section 4](#)). In addition, [ArchProfile:absoluteDating](#) and [ArchProfile:currentStatus](#) may be included in `DataCite:Date`.

3.4 DataCite:relatedIdentifier

Rather than create a property that may not match well with the DataCite Metadata Schema, the Archaeology CoP took the decision that the recommended `ArchProfile:Relations` property should basically follow `DataCite:relatedIdentifier`. Hence, there is an almost 1:1 mapping between these properties and their subproperties, the caveats being that

- If `relationType = 'HasMetadata' or 'IsMetadataFor'` is used, then the related metadata schema and the schema URI need to be extracted from `ArchProfile:Relations.relatedMetadataScheme` to complete `DataCite.relatedIdentifier.relatedMetadataScheme` and `schemeURI`, respectively.
- The value used in `ArchProfile:Relations.relatedResource` may need to be mapped to the most appropriate equivalent if it does not exactly match any of the controlled list values of `DataCite:relatedIdentifier.resourceTypeGeneral`. If an equivalent of the value does not exist, then `DataCite:relatedIdentifier.resourceTypeGeneral = 'Other'`, with the value supplied as the `resourceType`.

[Note: It is strongly encouraged to add a 'HasMetadata' `relationType` attribute in `DataCite:relatedIdentifier`, pointing to the sample metadata structured according to `ArchProfile`.]

It is questioned by Archaeology CoP as to whether the controlled vocabulary used for `DataCite:relatedIdentifier.relationType` describes well all of the relationships needed for material samples, and a review by the wider samples community is encouraged.

3.5 DataCite:Description

The free-text `ArchProfile:Description` property is used to record descriptive information about the sample not captured elsewhere. It maps to `DataCite:Description` with `descriptionType = 'Abstract'`.

Other `ArchProfile` properties that may be included in `DataCite:Description` are:

- [ArchProfile:Project](#)
- [ArchProfile.collectionMethod](#)
- [ArchProfile:stratigraphicContext](#)
- [ArchProfile:sampleDepth](#)
- [ArchProfile:Colour](#)
- [ArchProfile:currentStatus](#)

3.6 DataCite:geoLocation

The Archaeology CoP again decided that the mandatory `ArchProfile:Project.siteLocation` property—'The location from where the sample was collected, as accurately as possible'—should follow the structure of `DataCite:geoLocation`. Consequently, there is an equivalency between them.

4. ArchProfile Mandatory Properties

Because of being held in recommended or optional DataCite Metadata Schema properties, it is clear that it may not be possible to complete all of the mandatory properties in the Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile from an IGSN ID metadata record. The purpose of this Recommendation, however, is to ensure high-quality, complete metadata for an archaeological sample registered with an IGSN ID using DataCite. If the opposite becomes a requirement/norm, `ArchProfile` will be re-examined and updated by the Archaeology CoP.

4.1 ArchProfile:Project

`ArchProfile:Project` contains 'The title (and any alternatives) of the site or project'. It is not clear from the IGSN–DataCite Crosswalk Recommendation as to where this information might be for a typical IGSN ID metadata record encoded in the DataCite Metadata Schema. However, if this exists, it will be most likely captured in `DataCite:Description` with `descriptionType = 'Abstract'`.

`ArchProfile:Project` also includes the mandatory `siteLocation` subproperty; the location where the sample was collected. This maps to `DataCite:geoLocation`. The recommended subproperties of `ArchProfile:Project` are crosswalked as follows:

- `ArchProfile:Project.projectDescription = DataCite.Description[descriptionType = 'Abstract']`.
- `ArchProfile:Project.agencyIdentifier = DataCite.alternateIdentifier` with `alternateIdentifierType = 'Agency ID'`.
- `ArchProfile:Project.siteTemporalCoverage = DataCite:Subject` and `ArchProfile:Project.siteTemporalCoverage.temporalClassification = DataCite:Subject.subjectScheme` and/or `schemeURI`.
- `ArchProfile:Project.siteType = DataCite:Subject` and `ArchProfile:Project.siteType.siteClassification = DataCite:Subject.subjectScheme + schemeURI + valueURI + classificationCode` (i.e., a concatenation of the values in these subproperties).

4.2 ArchProfile:investigationDates

All event dates for a material sample are contained in `DataCite:Date`, with the specific type of event held in the mandatory `DataCite:Date.dateType` subproperty. `dateType` does not include a direct equivalent of `ArchProfile:investigationDates` and its mandatory `startDate` and `endDate` subproperties, but could be captured in `DataCite:Date` with `dateType = 'Other'` and `dateInformation = 'Investigation Dates', 'Investigation start', or 'Investigation end'`.

Note that a mapping to `DataCite:Date.dateType = 'Coverage'` is deliberately avoided because `ArchProfile:investigationDates` refers to the collection site, whereas the material sample is the research output being registered. `dateType = 'Coverage'` is instead used to capture the absolute dating of the sample (see [ArchProfile:absoluteDating](#)).

4.3 ArchProfile:collectorExcavator

ArchProfile:collectorExcavator and DataCite:Creator properties are considered to be equivalent.

4.4 ArchProfile:Publisher

ArchProfile:Publisher = DataCite:Publisher.

4.5 ArchProfile:sampleTitle

DataCite:Title is the closest match for ArchProfile:sampleTitle. However, there is not a direct equivalency here, and some title information for an archaeological sample may be held in other DataCite properties.

4.6 ArchProfile:otherIdentifier

ArchProfile:otherIdentifier contains 'The project / reference / catalogue / sample number(s) used to identify the sample on site'. Any such local identifiers assigned to a material sample are captured in DataCite:alternateIdentifier.

4.7 ArchProfile:collectionDate

ArchProfile:collectionDate = DataCite:Date [dateType = 'Collected'].

4.8 ArchProfile:sampleMaterialType

From the IGSN-DataCite Crosswalk Recommendation, the materials that compose the sample (i.e., what is contained in ArchProfile:sampleMaterialType) are contained in DataCite:Subject for IGSN IDs. Related values in the DataCite:Subject.subjectScheme, schemeURI, valueURI, and classificationCode subproperties are concatenated to form ArchProfile:sampleMaterialType.materialClassification.

5. ArchProfile Recommended Properties

5.1 ArchProfile:investigationType

It is expected that the investigation type(s) for an archaeological sample follow a standard vocabulary. ArchProfile:investigationType should therefore be held in DataCite:Subject, with the typology information for the mandatory investigationClassification subproperty captured in

`DataCite:Subject.subjectScheme, schemeURI, valueURI, and classificationCode.`

5.2 ArchProfile:Contributor

`ArchProfile:Contributor = DataCite:Contributor.`

5.3 ArchProfile:Description

`ArchProfile:Description = DataCite:Description[descriptionType = 'Abstract'].`

5.4 ArchProfile:Subject

`ArchProfile:Subject = DataCite:Subject`, with the latter's subproperties concatenated for `ArchProfile:Subject.subjectClassification`.

5.5 ArchProfile:collectionMethod

`DataCite.Description` with `descriptionType = 'Methods'` should contain both `ArchProfile.collectionMethod` and its `sampleHousing` subproperty. Since `collectionMethod` is fixed and may follow a standard vocabulary, it could additionally be repeated in `Subject`.

If included, then `ArchProfile:collectionMethod.samplePhoto` would be captured in `DataCite` as a `RelatedIdentifier` with `relatedIdentifierType = 'URL'`, `relationType = 'IsDocumentedBy'`, and `resourceTypeGeneral = 'Image'`. Associated reuse information for `samplePhoto`—as required by its mandatory `photoLicence` subproperty—should then be held in `DataCite:Rights`.

The CoP understands that including reuse information of photographs/images associated with the material sample stretches the definition of `DataCite:Rights`, as this property should contain rights for the resource being registered (i.e., the sample itself). However, it is uncertain how photographs/images will be shared and whether licence information can be explicitly tied to them. At the same time, it is clear that those accessing sample metadata ideally need to have reuse information to hand rather than searching for it within each photograph/image.

5.6 ArchProfile:stratigraphicContext

From the IGSN–DataCite Crosswalk Recommendation, information about a material sample at its 'birth' should be included in `DataCite:Description`. In particular,

`descriptionType = 'Abstract'` is used to provide 'A brief description of the resource and the context in which it was created'. Therefore, `ArchProfile:stratigraphicContext` and its recommended and optional subproperties should be concatenated within `DataCite:Description[descriptionType = 'Abstract']`, with the exception of:

- `ArchProfile:stratigraphicContext.siteDiagram`, which is linked as a `DataCite:relatedIdentifier` with `relatedIdentifierType = 'URL'`, `relationType = 'IsDocumentedBy'`, and `resourceTypeGeneral = 'Image'`. `DataCite:Rights` would then contain `siteDiagram` reuse information for its mandatory `siteDiagramLicence` subproperty. See [ArchProfile:collectionMethod](#) concerning inclusion of photograph/image reuse information.
- `ArchProfile:stratigraphicContext.soilTexture`, which should be described following agreed standards and hence be in `DataCite:Subject` with the information needed for `ArchProfile:stratigraphicContext.soilTexture.soilClassification` in `DataCite:Subject.subjectScheme`, `schemeURI`, `valueURI`, and `classificationCode`.

5.7 ArchProfile:sampleDepth

`ArchProfile:sampleDepth` and its subproperties—`depthUnits` (mandatory) and `depthReferencePoint` (recommended)—should be concatenated and provided in `DataCite:Description` with `descriptionType = 'Abstract'`.

5.8 ArchProfile:sampleWeight

Although stretching the DataCite Metadata Schema definition slightly, the Archaeology CoP believe that the free-text `DataCite:Size` property is best utilized to capture `ArchProfile:sampleWeight`, concatenated with its `weightUnits` and `weightConditions` subproperties.

5.9 ArchProfile:Colour

Combined information from `ArchProfile:Colour` and its subproperties are expected to be available in `DataCite:Description[descriptionType = 'Abstract']`. As `ArchProfile:Colour` is expected to follow a community-agreed vocabulary, this property—and its `colourClassification` subproperty—could additionally be repeated in `Subject`.

5.10 ArchProfile: absoluteDating

The 'Numerical age or range (start/end dates) of the sample' captured in ArchProfile: absoluteDating maps to DataCite:Date [dateType = 'Coverage']. DataCite:Date.dateInformation then holds ArchProfile: absoluteDating.datingMethod and datingClassification. Again, these two subproperties might be repeated in Subject.

5.11 ArchProfile: relativeDating

Maps to DataCite:Subject with ArchProfile: relativeDating.datingClassification a concatenation of DataCite:Subject.subjectScheme, schemeURI, valueURI, and classificationCode.

5.12 ArchProfile: currentStatus

ArchProfile: currentStatus and its storageLocation subproperty should be contained in DataCite:Description with descriptionType = 'TechnicalInfo'. In alignment with the IGSN-DataCite Crosswalk Recommendation, if the sample has been (for example) discarded or destroyed, this is also included in DataCite:Date with dateType = 'Other' and an appropriate description in dateInformation.

ArchProfile: accessConditions are captured in DataCite:Rights and its subproperties, according to whether the access conditions follow a controlled vocabulary.

5.13 ArchProfile: Relations

As stated in [§3.4](#), ArchProfile: Relations and DataCite:RelatedIdentifier are equivalent to all intents and purposes.

Annex A – CoP Members

The IGSN-DataCite Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Community of Practice is composed of the following members:

- Rorie Edmunds (DataCite)[Ex officio & Co-chair]
- Jens Klump (Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation & IGSN e.V.)[Ex officio & Co-chair] – <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5911-6022>

- Bjørn Bartholdy (TU Delft, the Netherlands) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3985-1016>
- Penny Crook (Co-founder, Electronic Field Notebooks) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8509-7865>
- Anthony Corns (The Discovery Programme, Ireland) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0262-981X>
- Yiu-Kang (Gary) Hsu (Leibniz-Forschungsmuseum für Georessourcen/Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum, Bochum, Germany) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2439-4863>
- Christin Keller (Deutsches Archäologisches Institut, Berlin, Germany) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5727-0226>
- David Novák (Institute of Archaeology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6592-6291>
- Esther Plomp (University of Aruba, Research Center) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3625-1357>
- Thomas Rose (Leibniz-Forschungsmuseum für Georessourcen/Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum, Bochum, Germany) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8186-3566>
- Shawn Ross (Macquarie University, Sydney, Australia) - <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6492-9025>
- Jan Sessing (Leibniz-Forschungsmuseum für Georessourcen/Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum, Bochum, Germany) - <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-6648-350X>

We also acknowledge the following former CoP members for their contributions to this work: Stéphanie Duchêne, Barbara Trichereau, and Andrew Williams.